

WAYS TO ORGANIZE AND DEVELOP MARKETING RESEARCH IN THE LABOR MARKET

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Abstract. *In this article, in order to develop the right plan for the development of technical schools, the segmentation and location of the buyers of educational services, and the development of a strategic plan for the development of the educational institution have been developed.*

Keywords: *labor market, educational service, buyer, segment, development, strategy, education.*

ПУТИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И РАЗВИТИЯ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ НА РЫНКЕ ТРУДА

Аннотация. *В данной статье в целях разработки правильного плана развития техникумов разработана сегментация и расположение покупателей образовательных услуг, разработан стратегический план развития образовательного учреждения.*

Ключевые слова: *рынок труда, образовательная услуга, покупатель, сегмент, развитие, стратегия, образование.*

INTRODUCTION

The modern conditions of the activity of the educational institution are characterized by increasing instability, increasing uncertainty in the external environment, reduction of budget funds and increasing competition in the market of educational services. According to many scientists, an important tool for the successful operation of an educational institution can be the use of strategic planning. Most of the experts are concerned about the spread of existing strategic plans and strategies emphasizes that it is not sufficiently adapted to the changing market conditions, that the main attention is mainly focused on solving internal problems, and that the interaction with the consumers of educational services is weak. In order to improve the university activity planning system, in our opinion, it is necessary to use marketing tools more actively in making management decisions.

The most important marketing tool for making management decisions in an educational institution is marketing research of the educational services market. In order to unify information in the analytical stage of developing a strategic plan for the development of an educational institution, several existing methods of studying the market of educational services should be supplemented with the analysis of factors affecting the actions and decisions of two market subjects - consumers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our proposed methodology for studying the educational services market includes several stages.

1) At the first stage of the research, a marketing research concept is developed, which is a document reflecting the main idea of the research. The concession must justify the relevance of the research, determine its goals and tasks, the object and subject of the research, and indicate the time. Choosing and justifying methods, providing research with information is of great importance. A marketing research program is being developed based on the research concept.

2) In the second stage, according to the research concept, it is necessary to analyze the market of educational services: to assess the size of the market, its capacity, "corporate" structure, the level and seriousness of competition, and to identify the main trends. The task of a comprehensive study of the educational services market is to obtain complete information about the market, its characteristics and development trends. An important stage of the research can be an expert survey, which allows not only subjective, but also objective analysis of the situation in the market of educational services, its development prospects, factors affecting consumers and purchases. Heads of educational institutions, employees of the region's education, youth policy and others can participate as experts.

3) At the third stage of research, it is necessary to analyze the actions of consumers of educational services: life goals, interests, evaluations, desires, motivations for actions, preferences and aspirations related to their internal value system. By studying their consumers, their wishes and privileges, Technical Colleges can offer them exactly what they need and do it better than their competitors. The main task in studying the consumer is to identify the factors affecting their behavior and to analyze the purchasing behavior models (the decision-making process and motives for choosing educational services).

In order to successfully compete in the market of educational services, the management of Pasdargom Service Technical College should know in advance the changes in the wishes of consumers, if not in the educational program, to make timely changes in the equipment of the educational process, organization of consumers. This information is the communication of the educational institution. It is especially important to develop a marketing and pricing policy, to form a brand. It is necessary to know exactly what is valuable and important for the consumers in shaping the advertising message, developing the advertising activity.

In most markets, less expensive purchases are made or the consumer and buyer can act as one person, and this information may be sufficient to make management decisions. In the market of educational services, it is necessary to analyze the actions of another target audience - buyers of educational services. Studying buyers is one of the most important types of research, because it is they who bring the main benefit to the educational institution by influencing the choice of the consumer and purchasing the educational service. Therefore, regardless of its size and specific features of its activity, the customer is the center of attention of any successful organization. In order to develop the right plan for the development of the technical school, it is necessary to identify the most attractive segments in order to segment the buyers of educational services and determine their location. It is necessary to evaluate the level of influence of various factors at the stages of the purchase decision-making process. It is necessary to analyze the price and other assumptions of buyers.

4) On the basis of data analysis, it is necessary to create a detailed portrait of the consumer of educational services, to distinguish the types and factors of the actions of consumers in the market of educational services. The result of the analysis of the buying behavior should be the segmentation of buyers and the evaluation of the factors of buying behavior in the market.

5) The first stage of research is the development of recommendations for the development of a strategic plan for the development of an educational institution. Also, it is necessary to analyze the research conducted at this stage, the difficulties and mistakes encountered, and develop recommendations for further marketing research.

RESULTS

In recent years, the analysis of the state of the market of educational services in the Samarkand region made it possible to identify the main trends in the development of this market:

The market of educational services in the region is represented by a number of educational institutions of primary, secondary and professional education. The activities of all institutions are interconnected to a certain extent: consumers of primary vocational education may become consumers of secondary and secondary specialized and professional education in the future.

Brief information about educational institutions

2022 as of January

No	Educational institutions	TM number	TM strength	Number of available students (2020/2021 academic year)	Filling coefficient
1	Vocational schools	37	24190	17479	0.7
2	Technical schools	23	20220	15688	0.8
3	Colleges	14	11605	8664	0.8
	Total	74	56015	4181	0.8

In Samarkand region, the potential demand for secondary specialized and professional education services is 41,831 people, but this indicator is constantly decreasing. This is explained by the increasing coverage of family education on the one hand, and the fact that middle school education is paid for on the other hand. The level of migration cannot significantly improve the situation, because the level of emigration is quite high. Against the backdrop of steady decline in demand, the obvious imbalance of this market is an increase in supply. According to statistical data, the offer in the educational services market of Samarkand region in January 2022 amounted to 56,015 people. The price equivalent to the offer in the market is the capacity of the educational services market in the region. A reduction in market opportunities leads to a fiercely competitive environment, which is particularly evident in the field of vocational training. This is also related to the increase in the number of non-state universities. Analyzing the competitive environment of the province gave an opportunity to evaluate it according to two main indicators: the material and technical base of technical schools (the presence of their own territory equipped for the educational process) and the number of students. From the point of view of the material and technical base of technical schools, the market of educational services is described as medium concentration. 74 professional educational institutions in the region from 1998 to today received 26 billion 822 million soums from the Republic and local budgets, including 15 billion 866 million soums from loans from foreign countries, a total of 42 billion 708 million soums for educational laboratories, computer equipment, cars and tractors technique, equipped with mini workshop and workshop equipment. These devices are used in the training process.

DISCUSSION

Analyzing the portfolio of educational services of regional market entities showed that the specialties required in technical schools are healthcare (67%), engineering (11.7%), business and management (3.7%), agriculture, forestry and fisheries (2.9), architecture and construction.

(2.7%), veterinary medicine (2.7%), computer technologies and informatics (2.6%), service and transport (3.3%), law (1.2%), environmental protection and agricultural machinery (0.8%), production and communication, information (1.2%). Medical and engineering specialties (nursing, paramedic-midwifery, pharmaceuticals, installation of water and sewage systems, installation of gas networks, real estate registration) make up the largest share in the training of middle-level specialists.

About the number of students studying full-time education at technical schools in Samarkand region INFORMATION

T/ r	Number of educational fields	Total education the number of children	so:		From the total number of students					
			run lat grant	payment account cancel	1st step			2nd stage		contract
					Total	grant	contract	Total	grant	
	Total by region:	14599	2325	12274	6773	1306	5395	7714	992	6722
1	Pedagogy - 110,000	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
2	Art - 210,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	Humanities - 220,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	Journalism and social information - 310,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Business and management - 320,000	552	142	410	217	85	132	335	57	278
6	Rights - 330,000	184	27	157	72	0	0	0	0	0
7	Natural sciences - 410,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Engineering work - 510,000	1720	286	1434	938	162	776	782	124	658
9	Computer technologies and informatics - 520,000	384	188	196	151	107	44	233	81	152
10	Production and processing industries - 530,000	133	78	55	66	39	27	67	39	28
11	Architecture and construction - 540,000	395	131	264	178	85	93	217	46	171
12	Communication and information, telecommunication technologies - 550,000	41	9	32	17	5	12	24	4	20
13	Agriculture, forestry and	431	274	157	143	113	30	28	1	127

	fisheries - 610,000							8	6	
14	Agricultural machinery - 620,000	91	65	26	29	23	6	62	4	20
15	Veterinary medicine - 630,000	387	217	170	135	135	0	25	8	170
16	Agricultural irrigation and melioration - 640,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	Healthcare - 710,000	9777	609	9168	4600	441	4159	51	1	500
18	Social security - 720,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	Service - 810,000	264	195	69	93	36	57	17	1	12
20	Transport - 820,000	215	88	127	119	63	56	96	2	71
21	Environment - 830,000	24	15	9	14	11	3	10	4	6
22	Security of vital activities - 840,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

There is a significant gender difference in the selection of specialties, which is especially noticeable in the selection of a profession in secondary and higher educational institutions. So, among the students studying in education, healthcare, culture and art, economy and management, women made up 74-80%. Males predominate (79-92%) among the students studying higher and secondary engineering-technical education in such specialties as motor vehicles, geology, mineral exploration and exploitation, energy, energy and electrical engineering, metallurgy, mechanical engineering and material processing, automation. In the labor market, graduates with primary and higher vocational education are in greater demand than those with secondary vocational education.

5 professional educational institutions in the 2020-2021 academic year 194 junior specialists graduated. The address of residence, passport information of the graduates was collected and a list of names was created.

Today, 185 of the 194 graduates of professional educational institutions (95.4%) have been employed.

Of them, 181 people (93.3%) were employed, 4 people (2.1.0%) entered family educational institutions.

Among the employed graduates, 101 are employed in enterprises and organizations, 25 are working as sole entrepreneurs, 22 are running family businesses, and 33 are engaged in real estate business.

CONCLUSIONS

It is possible to determine the most demanded specialties in the labor market. Professionals of workers for work in mining, production, agriculture, construction and transport and communication fields in primary vocational training. In secondary vocational education -

automation and management, culture and art, education and pedagogy, economy and management, construction and architecture, vehicles. The specialties most in demand in the labor market in higher professional education are metallurgy, mechanical engineering, material processing, vehicles, informatics and computer technologies, instrumentation and optics engineering, automation and control, construction and architecture, education and pedagogy, culture and art, energy, energy. and electrical engineering.

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